
REVIEW OF RESEARCH ON PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENTS

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Abstract: The article examines the problem of personality in the context of specific historical conditioning. A retrospective analysis of studies was carried out, through everyday knowledge, as well as achievements of science, technology and information technology, representing the results of the growth of human self-awareness. The authors' works on personal developments are presented.

Key words: personality, theories, principles, phenomenon, holistic approach, understanding of the problem.

ОБЗОР ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ ЛИЧНОСТНЫХ НОВООБРАЗОВАНИЙ

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Аннотация: В статье проблема личности рассматривается в контексте конкретно-исторической обусловленности. Проведен ретроспективный анализ исследований, посредством обыденных знаний, а также, достижений науки, техники и информационных технологий представляющих результаты роста человеческого самосознания. Представлены работы авторов, посвященных личностным новообразованиям.

Ключевые слова: личность, теории, принципы, феномен, целостный подход, осмысление проблемы.

INTRODUCTION

The nature of personality is an ontogenetic acquisition of a person, the result of a complex process of his social development. This understanding of personality determines the main principle in considering and solving problems of its formation - the principle of development. Acting as the highest type of movement, development is not just a general and eternal growth, increase, but a qualitative new formation, distinguished by a number of certain patterns. The process of development is, firstly, progressive in nature, when the stages already passed seem to repeat the known

features and properties of the lower ones, but repeat them at a higher level. contradictions and leads through a leap to a new stage of development with interdependence and inextricable connection of all aspects of the developing phenomenon. Secondly, development is characterized by irreversibility, not by copying, but by movement at a new level, a new turn of the spiral, when the results of previous development are realized. Thirdly, development is a unity of struggling opposites, which are the internal driving force of the development process. We are talking about the contradiction in the very essence of objects as the principle of all self-motion. It is the resolution of internal contradictions that leads through a leap to a new stage of development with the interdependence and inextricable connection of all aspects of the developing phenomenon.

In the system of general humanities, the principle of development acts rather as a psychological one, and due to its specificity, it is assumed not just to study, but to manage the process of personality formation, the formation of which acts as a special type of development, which has its own tendencies, prospects for development, self-determination, and self-realization.

The problem of personal developments is viewed through the prism of various parameters. If we are based on an understanding of the specific historical conditionality and socio-economic determinism of the individual, then it should be considered in close connection with the development of society as a social being, a member of a particular society, a conscious, socially responsible subject.

In the process of personality development, the versatility of changes manifests itself - progressive and regressive, irreversible and successive, repeating well-known features of the lower, giving a recombination of existing elements, etc. Spiral and stepwise translational motion is characterized by discontinuous (qualitative) and continuous (quantitative) changes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the 20th century in all studies of mental processes, the personal principle began to prevail; it is presented entirely as personality-oriented knowledge, according to the terminology of M. Polanyi [1], P. Feyerabend [2], etc. A personal basis is also present in studies of speech [3], thinking [4], memory [5], etc. And, if the works of the 60-70s, for example, V. Vilyunas about emotions [6], still focused on detailing the functions of emotions themselves, then research in the 80-90s of the 20th century included specific definitions of personal functions (emotions, will, etc.) in the context of the functioning of the personality.

Research aimed at studying human abilities and activities has had a significant impact on the problem of personal developments. Thus, in psychological science, a periodization was formulated in the logic of posing the problem of abilities: at the first stage, the relationship between abilities and activity was studied; on the second,

indicators of professionally important qualities were introduced, which played the role of a "transitional bridge" between abilities and activity (its requirements); at the third stage, abilities were determined not only by individual criteria and the criterion of social success of activity, but also by the criterion of subjectively acceptable success. The main conclusion: indicators of professionally important qualities and abilities are considered from the standpoint of their use by the individual himself in his way of relating to activity. This transformation of the problem was paradigmatic in relation to the field of personality psychology and all psychology.

In a similar functional way, K. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya approaches the explanation of "responsibility as a task necessary when carrying out activities that meet the aspirations of the individual for a certain time and in the presence of unforeseen difficulties" [7]. Similarly, she describes the very activity of a person as her vital ability to maintain herself as a subject of her life (or, in case of failure, to turn into its passive performer) [8].

In other words, whether we are talking about the volitional qualities of the individual, his abilities, responsibility, motivation or the property of being a subject of life. The definition of the functions of each of these personal abilities is given through the system of relations of the individual with the world - activity, value, etc., depending on the specific strategy that the individual chooses when implementing these relations.

Theoretical models of this kind, in which the parameters being studied (or the vectors of connections between these parameters) fit into a more general, dynamic system (of activity or relationships) that depends on the individual as a subject (his or her choices, preferences, decisions), are inextricably linked with the typological study of the individual and the construction of real typologies [9], etc.

The direction of such typological studies can be traced back to the first stages of the development of the problem of personality neoplasms, starting with A. Lazursky. They can be divided into two main trends that are interconnected: one of them aims to construct a typology (based on certain a priori grounds) and the other – theoretical and phenomenological identification and generalization of types existing in reality. For example, in the 60s of the 20th century, N. Reinwald defined three personality types: "creator", "consumer" and "destroyer" [9]; later this developed into a direction aimed at identifying the bases, parameters, structures that formed the basis of the typology of personality traits.

E. Golubeva, setting as her specific task the study of the abilities and inclinations of the individual, analyzes the general features of the typological approach and notes as one of the most important characteristics of Pavlov's typology the tendency to constantly compare the properties of higher nervous activity (HNA) and ideas about specific human types - an artist and a thinker. She proposes a model

that is based on three universal fundamental principles of abilities: two - activity and self-regulation with reference to N. Leites who identified them [10], and the third - direction with reference to B. Ananyev. In turn, it relies on four cross-cutting parameters of the personality structure: emotionality, activity, self-regulation and motivation, including motivation, temperament, abilities and character as substructures of the personality [7]. However, we emphasize that this typology is built on the basis of the connection "organism and personality", and not "personality - activity", which must be taken into account when comparing different typologies.

Thus, it is clear that when defining personality, researchers relied on three main characteristics: "activity", "self-regulation" and "focus" (as the highest indicators of personality integration, according to B. Ananyev, S. Rubinstein and others). Nevertheless, critical views were repeatedly expressed against the term "focus", which interpreted the personality category as a "dichotomy of collectivism and individualism", "amorphous description", etc., not conveying the full richness, contradictory complexity, and interactivity of personality. Subsequently, the concept of "focus" was replaced by "activity" [7].

The concept of activity was associated with the definition of personality as a subject of life and with the extent to which it becomes a subject. It was assumed that activity – depending on the extent to which a personality becomes a subject – has a typological character. For a more specific definition of activity, as was the case with the characterization of orientation, researchers identified two main forms of activity – initiative and responsibility, and empirically studied the relationship and nature of these forms. The corresponding typologies of initiative and responsibility revealed more subtle relationships between external and internal determinants of activity [11]. In addition, a hypothetical model of the structure of activity was developed, according to which activity was defined as a semantic integral of aspirations and achievements of a personality, but, unlike K. Levin and F. Hoppe, was designated as a link mediating them – self-regulation [7].

Leaving aside the historical sequence in the development of the problem of personality neoplasms, it can be noted that a previously outlined differentiation of a number of directions in the study of personality has occurred: one, in the direction of research into personality in activity (or sometimes, more precisely, research into the activity modalities of personality: target, attitudinal, dispositional, need-motivational and, of course, abilities); the other, in the direction of research into personality in communication, with the latter also being differentiated into real communication and the particularities of including in it ideal – "inter" and even "meta" – individual personality projections [12], etc.

Within the first direction, in turn, studies of personality and personality traits in cognitive activity are gradually distinguished (for example, the study of motivation

for learning activities undertaken by A. Markova), and studies of personality in such activities as professional, work, i.e. practical [7].

As before, in line with this trend, supporters of the activity approach (in its Leontiev version) are engaged in such a higher category as consciousness. These include studies devoted to the psychosemantics of the consciousness of the individual, cognized by the method of semantic differential, the special subject of which was not the individual in its scientific-psychological understanding, but the implicit personality that exists in everyday consciousness, or the emotional-figurative representation of the individual [13].

An important feature of such studies can be considered the fact that, carried out in the activity paradigm, they directly connect with the actual communicative modalities of the personality when it comes to the way of representing another person's personality in the consciousness. At the same time, within the direction of research "personality - activity" a differentiation occurs, which was insufficiently carried out in the concept of A. Leontiev: the internal activity characteristics of the personality are differentiated from the problems of including the personality in real activity.

Thus, summarizing theoretical studies of the phenomenon of personality, apparently, firstly, it is possible to talk about different stages of personality formation, without tying the general concept to one of them.

Secondly, it is necessary to talk about progressive and regressive development and state of personality (as V. Myasishchev believed, about its norm and pathology), but at the same time specifically about personality. And finally, thirdly: it is possible to propose various criteria for defining personality as essential, without opposing them to definitions of other authors.

Realizing the importance of the fact that the more multidimensional and multifaceted this set of definitions is, the deeper the penetration into the essence of personality will be. In addition, we emphasize that the problem of personality development includes another important aspect in its consideration - "taking into account age periods", where there are both constructive and destructive forms of development and its different levels.

It has been suggested that psychological science began, in a certain sense, with the study of the development of the child's personality, although, by general admission, despite the merits of A. Zaporozhets, D. Elkonin and others in the study of childhood psychology, the only complete theory of the child's personality in its development is considered to be the concept of L. Bozhovich. The most modern, based on empirical studies of the reconstruction of personality at the adolescent and youth stages of its development, is considered to be the concept of D. Feldstein. He clearly draws a line between the definition of the essence of personality and the

different directions, forms and methods of its development. As a result of a thorough empirical study of adolescents and young men, the author proposed a typology of the regressive direction of adolescent development, which is correlated with the ideal model of optimal development, which is valuable for teachers and educators [14].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A whole complex of studies of personality neoplasms in the modern system of training and education is carried out at the Psychological Institute of the Russian Academy of Education under the leadership of V. Rubtsov, aimed at creating a system of personality-oriented education (the title of the book by I. Yakimanskaya sounds almost the same) [15]. Modern interest in psychodiagnostics is connected not only with its practical value. It marks the need of psychology and psychologists to address the real personality and solve the indicated problem focusing on the diagnostics of the social environment in which personality traits and characteristics are formed and manifested through a functional-dynamic systemic approach to personality, expressed in the need to study it in real conditions of functioning.

In some specific areas of psychology, for example, in the field of political psychology, prototypes of political parties and leaders inherent in everyday consciousness are simultaneously identified, and then certain typologies of the latter are constructed [16]. Psychological portraits of personality, which were constructed by E. Kuzmin, allow us to increasingly move away from the ideological universal and utopian type of personality of the Soviet person, characteristic of the era of totalitarianism. On the one hand, they enrich the theoretical model of personality itself, on the other, they allow us to understand new aspects of the functioning of the personality in society, and not those outlined by the schematic triad transferred from American textbooks to domestic soil: "personality – society", "personality – group", "personality – personality" [17].

In addition, it should be noted that sociological science is updating research aimed at studying the nature of changes in the social type of personality and the degree of its freedom depending on the social system [18], the state of autonomous factors of socialization of the individual in different social systems [19]; the status of the individual in the organization [20]; the patterns of social interaction of individuals in different social groups [21]; special properties of needs, motives and value orientations of the individual that contribute to the regulation of its social behavior, etc. The latter are common to sociology and social psychology, therefore the boundary between them is largely arbitrary. The study of the social system allows us to understand the value orientations of the individual, the possible degree of its creative manifestation. However, social behavior is determined not only by the current position of the person, but also by his past life experience, as well as the nature of the cultural values that he has adopted, in which the previous history of

mankind is accumulated. Each individual as a person is a product not only of existing relationships, but also of all previous history, as well as his own development and self-awareness. The same social position in its objective features, being differently realized and assessed by the person, encourages him to different actions. Hence the general tendency of modern philosophy and psychology to consider the personality not so much "from the outside" as "from the inside", not as a given, but as a search, not as something created, but as a creative, active principle.

The latest sociological and psychological studies examining personality development throughout its life path show its stability and at the same time plasticity, the ability to self-change [22].

The works of Kazakhstani scientists who use a comprehensive approach to the study of the problem of personality development are noteworthy. Their main goal is to study the psychological foundations in the development of a creative intellectual personality in an educational environment, as well as to study the problem of developing abilities, the psyche and personality as a whole [23].

A. Satova focuses on the psychology of a gifted individual. According to the author, a comprehensive study of gifted youth allows us to develop theoretical foundations for diagnostics and programs for the personal development of gifted individuals, principles of a personality-oriented and prognostic approach to examining the potential capabilities of an individual at the adolescent stage of development. According to A. Satova, the development of giftedness is possible only with the implementation of a personal approach at all levels of socio-psychological and pedagogical influence, thanks to which it is possible to achieve the creation of a model of a highly intellectual, competitive, self-sufficient individual. In addition, the problem of developing abilities, the psyche, and personality as a whole was further developed in the creative research of Ch. Valikhanov, I. Altynsarin, A. Kunanbaev, Zh. Aimaurov, M. Dulatov, M. Zhumabaev, and others [24].

Well-founded approaches to understanding the problem of personality neoplasms in the light of the concept of social and spiritual foundations in the education of youth were expressed by E. Babamuratov and Sh. Particular attention is paid to the philosophical aspect of the personal development of youth, which was covered in the works of H. Shaikhova [26]. In the context of social activity and the formation of the personality of youth, the studies of Z. Kadyrova [27] deserve attention. Age periodization and socialization formed the basis of the works of F. Musaev [28]. In the works of Uzbek scientists, the problem of personality development is studied in the context of fundamental ideological changes in modern society, pluralism of opinions, the nature of the expression of social activity of young people, alternative behavior in the implementation of personal potential, etc.

In recent years, attempts have been made to determine the possibilities of the creative (transformative) potential of the individual. An important component of this phenomenon is the recognition of the conditions of influence of the modern social situation on the motive in the form of "the desire for the significance of one's own personality and self-esteem", which becomes the leading meaning-forming component for the assertion of the position of a young person in the system of social relations. Its formation is conditioned by the selective focus of life goals, needs, attitudes, ideals of youth, the manifestation of alternative behavior for the realization of creative possibilities, special abilities, etc. Any omission and underestimation of personal formations, in our opinion, can lead to pedagogical and psychological "neglect" of youth, unformed life positions, the manifestation of personal infantilism, the absence of independence in self-expression and self-affirmation, etc. [29].

In Uzbekistan, the problem of personal neoplasms is studied in the context of scientific implementation of the concept of forming a morally holistic and spiritually rich personality with an independent worldview and independent thinking, based on the spiritual heritage of the people and universal human values. This is explained by the fact that in the context of socio-economic, political, legal, historical-cultural, spiritual and educational transformations, issues of self-awareness, self-determination, self-realization with a link to youth are becoming more relevant. The state programs implemented in the country enhance the importance of the idea of forming a comprehensively developed and independently thinking individual with his own views, choices and strong civic positions. In this regard, the President of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized that the country will continue the state youth policy, raise it to an even higher level in accordance with the requirements of today, mobilize all the forces and capabilities of the state and society so that the youth have independent thinking, high intellectual and spiritual potential, are not inferior to their peers from other countries in any area, are happy and confident in their future [30]. It was also noted that our multinational people are selflessly working for the prosperity of our Motherland, building the foundation of a new Renaissance of Uzbekistan. On this path, our main support is the youth, who enter adulthood with great hopes and plans. The youth in the full sense of the word are the pride of the country, the creators of the bright future of the countries [31].

These words reflect the essence of the state policy implemented in Uzbekistan during the years of independence, the main priority of which has become concern for the education of a harmoniously developed, physically healthy and spiritually mature, intellectually rich young generation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study of general theoretical, general scientific, theoretical and methodological materials on the problem of personality neoplasms, analysis of

scientific trends, theories, concepts, approaches, models, as well as a comparative analysis of the achievements of scientists of different times, without diminishing the dignity and contribution of each of them, we will allow ourselves to make the following theoretical conclusions.

Firstly. The existing fundamental studies on the problem of personality neoplasms as a holistic scientific-theoretical and scientific-methodological database represent a bank of substantiated ideas, hypotheses, evidence regarding the "problems of personality development" in general, and "personality" in particular. The conducted retrospective analysis of socio-philosophical and psychological studies (based on a comparative analysis of scientific works carried out in the 60s-90s of the 20th century and the first decade of the 21st century) actualizes the degree of elaboration of the problem under study.

Secondly. The studies conducted at the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st centuries actualize the historical significance of the "personality" as an object of scientific knowledge and as a subject of society, reflecting dynamic changes in society, in the sphere of life, accompanied by the emergence of new systems of connections and relations (primarily due to the expanding information space), new challenges of the time. A deep understanding of the problem of personality development at the level of both everyday knowledge and scientific knowledge accumulated in the field of the humanities, as well as in the field of achievements of science, technology and information technology, as well as as a result of the growth of human self-awareness, becomes a reason for identifying new characteristics of the subject, object, goals and research tasks of the problem under study.

Thirdly. New characteristics of scientific research of scientists are achieved through the restructuring of mentality, change of goals, values, orientations, emergence of new needs, possibilities of the individual, etc. This fact acquires great importance, firstly, in the context of affirmation of the idea of cultural-historical determinacy of personal development of a person (according to L. Vygotsky), secondly, importance of multidimensional structured and widely understood socio-cultural definition of it (the theory of D. Feldstein). This actualizes the importance of psychological science in defining new tasks in cognition of a person, as an actively acting subject (in defining the topic of this study the author started from Vygotsky's cultural-historical idea of personality development).

Fourthly. As the data show, in the 20th century the problem of personality became the main one in a number of directions of foreign philosophy. Characteristic for them was the recognition of the metaphysical division of personality into social and individual components, functional and actually personal, creative. The most complete type of modern research abroad is contained in the concepts of socialization

of the individual, the active development of which began in the mid-50s of the last century.

Fifthly. Modern dialectical-logical philosophy of the 21st century gives a holistic concept of personality as a socio-historical phenomenon and a general definition of personality as a holistic, multifaceted, multi-level formation, which can serve at the present stage as a methodological basis for studying various aspects of the problem of personality development within the framework of specific scientific disciplines.

Sixthly. The definition of personality in modern psychological science is a complex and multifaceted problem. The ideas about personality and its development in the process of ontogenesis have found their embodiment in a large number of scientific directions, theories and schools, distinguished by the originality of approaches, research methods and interpretations of the very concept of "personality", its structure, mechanisms and factors of development. Existing studies indicate the constant development within the framework of the humanitarian focus of the systemic, typological, activity-based, personality-oriented, age-based approaches.

Seventhly. In Uzbekistan, the problem of personality neoplasms is studied in the context of the formation of a harmoniously developed personality, which is one of the main priority tasks of the state. Research by Uzbek scientists is based on a comprehensive philosophical-social-spiritual concept of educating a perfect personality, carried out systematically, purposefully, through the prism of various scientific-theoretical approaches and directions.

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